

Autoregressive-Conditioned Diffusion for Semi-Supervised Thyroid Ultrasound Segmentation with Optical Flow-Based Pseudo Labels

Xiaorui Liu¹, Yijun Yang¹, Yingjing Xu², Lei Zhu^{1,3,*}

¹The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (Guangzhou)

²Zhejiang University ³The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology

Abstract

Ultrasound video segmentation plays a vital role in clinical diagnosis and treatment planning, yet the process is severely hindered by the high cost of manual annotation. Semi-supervised learning leverages limited labels effectively, but suffers from noisy pseudo-labels in low-contrast frames and lacks global modeling, leading to blurred boundaries and temporal inconsistencies in video segmentation. To this end, we propose a novel semi-supervised framework. We begin with a bidirectional optical flow-based pseudo-labeling strategy that fuses forward and backward warped masks using task-aware confidence weighting. To enhance spatial coherence, a diffusion model is employed to denoise the pseudo-labels in the latent space. Most importantly, we introduce a Visual Autoregressive (VAR) Encoder, a Transformer-based temporal modeling module that extracts cross-frame contextual priors from image latents. These priors are injected into every block of a DiT-based diffusion backbone via cross-attention, leveraging DiT’s strong global modeling capacity to refine spatial details while enforcing temporal consistency. Additionally, a YOLO-based post-processing step removes background artifacts by isolating the region of interest (ROI). Experimental results on a newly collected dataset of 80 patients and public datasets demonstrate that our framework achieves superior segmentation accuracy and temporal stability compared to existing semi-supervised methods.

1. Introduction

Ultrasound video segmentation is essential for computer-aided diagnosis and surgical planning [1, 2, 30, 58]. However, the intrinsic characteristics of ultrasound imaging—low tissue contrast, speckle noise, and motion artifacts—pose significant challenges to achieving robust and accurate segmentation [26]. Fully supervised mod-

els achieve high performance but require dense pixel-wise annotations, which are costly and time-consuming, limiting their scalability in clinical settings. Semi-supervised learning has emerged as a practical alternative by leveraging sparse annotations, where various strategies—such as pseudo-labeling, consistency regularization, or hybrid approaches—propagate supervision to unlabeled frames. However, in ultrasound videos with texture ambiguity and indistinct boundaries, many existing methods still struggle to maintain both spatial accuracy and temporal consistency.

To facilitate clinically viable semi-supervised segmentation, we construct a thyroid ultrasound video dataset with expert-verified annotations. As shown in Fig. 1, each case comprises consecutive frames and corresponding masks, capturing the temporal evolution of thyroid nodules. This dataset provides a reliable benchmark for developing temporally-aware models under limited supervision.

Despite recent advances in semi-supervised segmentation [9, 40, 44, 48], three key challenges persist. **First**, within the pseudo-labeling paradigm, most optical-flow-based approaches rely on unidirectional propagation, making them vulnerable to cumulative drift: early-frame errors propagate and amplify over time, especially in low-contrast or fast-motion regions [32, 52, 59]. While bidirectional flow has been explored in other domains, it remains underutilized in ultrasound, where alignment is unstable and temporal artifacts are common. **Second**, although Transformer architectures such as ViViT [3] and certain 3D CNNs can capture temporal cues, many practical ultrasound segmentation pipelines still employ encoders with limited effective receptive fields or adopt per-frame prediction heads, which reduces robustness under speckle noise and hinders modeling of long-range semantic continuity. **Third**, frame-independent inference stages can lead to flickering or abrupt segmentation changes, which are unacceptable in clinical practice [43, 56].

To overcome the limitations of existing semi-supervised segmentation methods, we propose a unified framework that tightly integrates spatial-temporal modeling to address la-

*Corresponding author.

Figure 1. Representative cases from our dataset. Each column pair represents an ultrasound frame and its corresponding segmentation mask. The rows illustrate temporal progression within each case. All videos are acquired from patients with thyroid nodules by experienced ultrasound clinicians. Annotations are manually verified by three radiologists with over three years of experience.

bel noise, spatial instability, and temporal inconsistency. The framework begins with a bidirectional optical flow-based pseudo-labeling strategy, which propagates annotations across frames using task-aware weighting informed by grayscale intensity and boundary confidence. This effectively reduces label drift and improves temporal alignment. Building on this, a latent-space diffusion module progressively refines the pseudo-label representations, denoising them to suppress speckle artifacts and recover fine anatomical structures in low-contrast ultrasound images. To further enhance temporal modeling, a Visual Autoregressive (VAR) Encoder captures long-range dependencies across frames and injects this contextual information into a DiT-style latent diffusion backbone through cross-attention, promoting spatial coherence and inter-frame consistency. Additionally, a YOLO-based post-processing module isolates relevant anatomical regions, and a grayscale histogram-guided Task Token adaptively adjusts pseudo-label fusion according to frame quality. Together, these components enable robust and temporally stable segmentation under sparse supervision. Experiments on an in-house dataset of 80 patients demonstrate that our method consistently outperforms existing baselines in both segmentation accuracy and temporal consistency, underscoring its clinical potential.

Our main contributions can be summarized as three-fold:

- We propose a unified semi-supervised framework that integrates bidirectional pseudo-label propagation, latent-space diffusion refinement, and a Visual Autoregressive (VAR) encoder to jointly address label noise, spatial instability, and temporal inconsistency in ultrasound video segmentation.
- We construct a new in-house ultrasound video dataset of 80 patients with frame-level annotations, providing a valuable benchmark for evaluating spatiotemporal consistency under sparse supervision.
- Extensive experiments demonstrate that our method outperforms state-of-the-art semi-supervised approaches in both segmentation accuracy and temporal stability, highlighting its practical effectiveness in real-world clinical scenarios.

2. Related Work

2.1. Ultrasound Video Segmentation

Recent approaches have introduced innovative hybrid transformer-based algorithms that fuse transformative and convolutional layer techniques for medical image segmentation (*e.g.*, breast lesion, polyp) [5, 19, 20, 36, 45, 51, 54].

For thyroid segmentation in ultrasound images, Ma *et al.* [31] employed a region proposal network (RPN) with spatial pyramid RoIAlign to capture global and local features in ultrasound images, while Chi *et al.* [11] proposed a 2D Transformer-UNet that fuses multi-level features via a multiscale cross-attention transformer for thyroid gland segmentation. These algorithms skillfully manage the representations derived from high-definition medical images, however, they grapple with computational difficulties owing to complexity issues. Additionally, the direct application of such image segmentation methods may inadvertently overlook critical temporal context, thereby inducing temporal inconsistencies. In order to address temporal modeling in video-level segmentation, the innovative method of Space-Time Memory Networks (STM) [33] and its variants [10, 25] are introduced, employing a memory network to extract vital information from a time-based buffer composed of all previous video sequences. Building upon this methodology, DPSTT [23] integrates a memory bank with decoupled transformers to track temporal lesion movement in medical ultrasound videos. MemSAM [12] proposes a novel ultrasound video segmentation model by incorporating space-time memory into SAM and carrying temporal cues. The challenge in ultrasound video segmentation revolves around efficiently harnessing the wealth of temporal data available.

2.2. Medical Semi-supervised Learning

Semi-supervised learning has become increasingly important in medical image analysis, especially for segmentation tasks with limited annotations. Existing methods can be broadly categorized into pseudo-labeling [22, 24], consistency regularization [17, 49], contrastive learning [14, 47, 48], and hybrid strategies [34]. POPCORN [22] pioneers progressive pseudo-labeling by constructing a curriculum learning framework based on feature similarity between labeled and unlabeled samples, further enhanced by enforcing consistency across different feature scales. Self-Loop Uncertainty [24] pretrains encoders through self-supervised tasks and fuses multi-view predictions to sharpen boundaries. AMVLM [34] introduces multiplicity-aware vision-language alignment, generating text-guided initial masks with uncertainty-weighted iterative refinement for complex multi-target segmentation. MemSAM [12] establishes a memory-driven pseudo-label generation paradigm, where a prototypical memory bank storing anatomical priors is used to generate prompt-guided segmentation masks for unlabeled images, eliminating manual annotation.

2.3. Diffusion Models

Recently, the Diffusion model is well-known as a novel generative modeling approach for its superior achievements in image synthesis and generation tasks [13, 21, 27, 39, 55,

60]. In essence, Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPM) [21] adopted a parameterized Markov chain to optimize the lower variational bound on the likelihood function, which can simulate a diffusion process to iteratively improve the quality of target distribution than other generative models. DDIM [42] develops iterative implicit probabilistic models based on DDPM and introduces a deterministic sampling process for the trade-off between computational costs and sample quality. Very recently, a few pioneering works tried to adopt diffusion models for high-level perceptual tasks, such as image classification, segmentation and object detection [4, 6, 16, 18, 29, 46, 50, 53, 55, 57]. Han *et al.* [18] combine a denoising diffusion-based conditional generative model and a pre-trained conditional mean estimator for natural image classification and regression. Diff-UNet [50] utilizes the diffusion models to solve 3D medical image segmentation problems and designs a Step-Uncertainty Fusion (SUF) module during inference for the robustness of the diffusion model’s predictions. Their potential for high-level vision in medical videos has yet to be fully explored.

3. Method

3.1. Overview

Our framework addresses the challenges of semi-supervised ultrasound video segmentation by integrating bidirectional pseudo-label propagation, latent-space diffusion refinement, and temporal-contextual modeling. Specifically, we first generate pseudo-labels using a bidirectional optical flow strategy that fuses forward and backward warped masks with contrast-aware weighting. These labels are then denoised in the latent space via a diffusion model to improve spatial consistency and suppress speckle noise. To further enforce temporal coherence, we introduce a Visual Autoregressive (VAR) Encoder that extracts cross-frame priors, which are injected into a DiT-based diffusion backbone via cross-attention. Additionally, a grayscale histogram-guided Task Token adaptively adjusts pseudo-label fusion according to frame quality. Finally, a YOLO-based post-processing module eliminates background artifacts by refining the predicted masks based on detected anatomical regions. The overall pipeline ensures accurate, stable segmentation under limited supervision. Section 3.2 details the pseudo-labeling strategy, and Section 3.3 elaborates on the VAR-enhanced latent diffusion module and temporal consistency objective.

3.2. Bidirectional Optical Flow Pseudo-Labeling

High-quality pseudo-labels are critical for reliable semi-supervised video segmentation, particularly in the presence of noise and temporal variation. To ensure temporal alignment and spatial coherence, our framework adopts a three-

Optical Flow-Based Pseudo-Labeling

VAR-Enhanced Diffusion Model

Figure 2. Overview of the proposed framework. The framework consists of two main components: (1) **Bidirectional Optical Flow-Based Pseudo-Labeling**: RAFT optical flow propagates keyframe masks bidirectionally to generate pseudo-labels, and a contrast-aware mask fusion strategy is applied to reduce error accumulation and enhance boundary sharpness; (2) **VAR-Enhanced Diffusion Model**: The diffusion model refines pseudo-labels by denoising latent representations, improving segmentation consistency. A Visual Autoregressive (VAR) Encoder extracts temporal-aware latent tokens as additional conditional input to guide segmentation. A YOLO-based post-processing step removes background artifacts to enhance segmentation precision.

stage strategy. RAFT [43] estimates bidirectional optical flow to propagate ground truth masks forward and backward. These warped masks are fused using a contrast-aware weighting scheme, followed by a refinement step that suppresses noise and enhances boundary sharpness.

RAFT Optical Flow. We adopt RAFT [43] to compute dense optical flow between consecutive frames. In this work, RAFT is used in a frozen state without finetuning, initialized from weights pretrained on FlyingChairs and FlyingThings3D, which provide general motion priors applicable to ultrasound despite domain differences. Given two input frames I_t and I_{t+k} at timestamps t and $t+k$, the forward flow $\mathbf{F}_{t \rightarrow t+k} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 2}$, which represents the pixel-wise displacement from I_t to I_{t+k} , is defined as:

$$\mathbf{F}_{t \rightarrow t+k} = \mathcal{F}_\theta(I_t, I_{t+k}), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{F}_\theta(\cdot, \cdot)$ denotes the RAFT model parameterized by θ . This flow is then used to warp the segmentation mask M_t at time t to the target frame $t+k$:

$$\tilde{M}_{t+k} = \mathcal{W}(M_t, \mathbf{F}_{t \rightarrow t+k}), \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{W}(\cdot, \cdot)$ is a differentiable warping function implemented via bilinear interpolation. The resulting warped mask \tilde{M}_{t+k} serves as the initial pseudo-label for frame $t+k$.

This forward warping enables label propagation, but may introduce cumulative drift or occlusion-induced artifacts. To address this, we employ a bidirectional fusion strategy discussed below.

Warped Mask Fusion. To enhance pseudo-label accuracy near object boundaries, we compute forward flow $\mathbf{F}_{t \rightarrow t+k}$ and backward flow $\mathbf{F}_{t+k \rightarrow t}$ between frames I_t and I_{t+k} . Using the differentiable warping function $\mathcal{W}(\cdot, \cdot)$, we apply these flows to M_t and M_{t+k} to obtain two warped masks.

The final pseudo-label at frame $t+k$, denoted as $\tilde{M}_{t+k}^{\text{final}}$, is given by a weighted fusion:

$$\tilde{M}_{t+k}^{\text{final}} = \lambda \mathcal{W}(M_t, \mathbf{F}_{t \rightarrow t+k}) + (1 - \lambda) \mathcal{W}(M_{t+k}, \mathbf{F}_{t+k \rightarrow t}), \quad (3)$$

where $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ balances the contributions of forward and backward propagation. This bidirectional fusion aggregates complementary spatial cues and mitigates errors from flow inaccuracy and occlusion, which often degrade single-direction warping. Here, λ is only used in the fusion stage, computed from the grayscale histogram mean intensity via a linear mapping $f(h)$ to the range $[0.3, 0.7]$, which we found empirically to yield stable results.

Pseudo-label Refinement. After fusion, we further im-

prove boundary quality via a refinement operator $\mathcal{G}(\cdot)$:

$$\tilde{M}_{t+k}^{\text{refined}} = \mathcal{G}(\tilde{M}_{t+k}^{\text{final}}), \quad (4)$$

where $\mathcal{G}(\cdot)$ applies morphological filtering to remove small noisy regions and smooth edges, followed by binarization to enforce spatial consistency. Unlike the fusion step, this refinement does not reuse λ and operates directly on the fused mask. Its role is to ensure that the pseudo-labels used for training have clean, well-defined boundaries before entering the segmentation network. This step complements the latent diffusion module: refinement is performed *offline* during pseudo-label generation to provide high-quality supervision, while latent diffusion performs *online* denoising in the latent space during model prediction.

Algorithm 1 Bidirectional Optical Flow-Based Pseudo-Labeling

Require: Keyframe masks \mathcal{M}_K , video frames \mathcal{I} , pre-trained RAFT model \mathcal{F}_θ

Ensure: Pseudo-labels \mathcal{M}_P

- 1: **for** each keyframe t in \mathcal{M}_K **do**
 - 2: **for** each frame $t+k$ **do**
 - 3: Compute flows: $\mathbf{F}_{t \rightarrow t+k}, \mathbf{F}_{t+k \rightarrow t}$
 - 4: Warp masks: $\tilde{M}_{t+k}^f, \tilde{M}_{t+k}^b$
 - 5: Fuse: $\tilde{M}_{t+k}^{\text{final}} \leftarrow \lambda \tilde{M}_{t+k}^f + (1 - \lambda) \tilde{M}_{t+k}^b$
 - 6: Refine: $\tilde{M}_{t+k}^{\text{refined}} \leftarrow \mathcal{G}(\tilde{M}_{t+k}^{\text{final}})$
 - 7: Store: $\mathcal{M}_P[t+k] \leftarrow \tilde{M}_{t+k}^{\text{refined}}$
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: **end for**
 - 10: **return** pseudo-labels \mathcal{M}_P
-

To enhance fusion robustness under varying visual conditions, we adopt a contrast-aware weighting scheme. For each frame, we extract a 16-bin grayscale histogram $h \in \mathbb{R}^{16}$ and compute $\lambda = f(h)$ based on the histogram’s mean intensity.

The final pseudo-label is computed as:

$$\hat{M}_t = \lambda \cdot M_f + (1 - \lambda) \cdot M_b, \quad (5)$$

where M_f and M_b denote the forward- and backward-warped masks. High-contrast frames yield larger λ , promoting confident fusion; low contrast encourages conservative averaging to suppress drift.

This histogram-guided scheme adaptively adjusts fusion strength based on visual quality, improving pseudo-label reliability in challenging ultrasound scenes with blurred or ambiguous boundaries. The grayscale histogram statistics are also used to generate a *Task Token* that encodes frame quality, which is later provided as an additional conditioning signal to the diffusion model.

3.3. Diffusion Model Enhancement

Diffusion models demonstrate strong denoising capabilities, making them particularly suitable for ultrasound video segmentation under speckle noise and low contrast. We enhance a latent-space diffusion framework by integrating spatial features from a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) [7], temporal priors from a Visual Autoregressive (VAR) Encoder, and multi-branch conditioning within a DiT backbone. Fig. 2 (right) presents an overview of the proposed architecture.

Visual Autoregressive Encoder Conditioning. To incorporate temporal context into the denoising process, we design a Visual Autoregressive (VAR) Encoder. Its input consists of a temporal window of spatial latents $\{x_{\text{cond}}^{(t-k)}, \dots, x_{\text{cond}}^{(t+k)}\}$ centered at frame t , where each $x_{\text{cond}}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$ is derived from the VAE encoder [7] and encodes semantic visual features.

These tensors are concatenated along the temporal axis and reshaped into a sequence of tokens:

$$x_{\text{seq}} = \text{Concat}(x_{\text{cond}}^{(t-k)}, \dots, x_{\text{cond}}^{(t+k)}),$$

resulting in $x_{\text{seq}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N' \times d'}$, where N' denotes the number of tokens and d' the feature dimension. The sequence is processed by a lightweight Transformer with L_{VAR} self-attention layers to capture long-range temporal dependencies.

Subsequently, a linear projection maps the output to N compact temporal tokens:

$$\text{VAR}(x_{\text{seq}}) \rightarrow \{c_i\}_{i=1}^N, \quad c_i \in \mathbb{R}^d,$$

where each c_i represents motion-invariant semantic priors across frames. These tokens are incorporated into each DiT block via a dedicated cross-attention branch, alongside spatial features x_{cond} , noisy latents z_t , and the Task Token from histogram statistics, enabling joint modeling of spatial appearance, temporal dynamics, frame quality, and denoising signals.

Latent Representation Refinement. To facilitate semantic-level denoising, we perform diffusion in the latent space rather than in the pixel domain. Each pseudo-mask M_t is encoded into a latent representation $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{64 \times 64 \times 4}$ via the VAE. Gaussian noise $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$ is added to simulate the forward diffusion process:

$$z_t = \sqrt{\alpha_t} x_0 + \sqrt{1 - \alpha_t} \epsilon,$$

where α_t is the noise schedule coefficient at timestep t . The denoising model $\epsilon_\theta(z_t, t)$, implemented via DiT, is trained to estimate the added noise:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{diff}} = \mathbb{E}_{z_t, t} \left[\|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(z_t, t)\|^2 \right]. \quad (6)$$

The timestep t is encoded and injected into each DiT block using Adaptive LayerNorm (AdaLN) to provide explicit diffusion-step conditioning. In parallel, the VAE decoder reconstructs the mask \hat{M}_t from x_0 , supervised by a reconstruction loss and a Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VAE}} = \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| M_t - \hat{M}_t \right\|^2 \right], \quad \mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}} = D_{\text{KL}}(q(x_0|M_t)||p(x_0)), \quad (7)$$

where $q(x_0|M_t)$ denotes the approximate posterior, and $p(x_0)$ is the standard Gaussian prior.

The total segmentation loss is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{seg}} = \lambda_{\text{diff}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{diff}} + \lambda_{\text{VAE}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{VAE}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}}, \quad (8)$$

with λ_{diff} and λ_{VAE} as weighting coefficients.

Diffusion Transformer Backbone. We employ DiT [35], a Transformer-based diffusion architecture operating in the latent domain. Each frame I_t and pseudo-mask M_t is encoded into $x_{\text{cond}}, x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{64 \times 64 \times 4}$ by the VAE. The corrupted latent z_t is generated from x_0 as previously described.

Each DiT block, among a total of $L = 12$, comprises four attention branches: (1) self-attention over z_t to model internal structure, (2) cross-attention to x_{cond} for spatial context, (3) cross-attention to VAR-derived tokens $\{c_i\}$ for temporal context, (4) cross-attention to the Task Token for frame quality context. All branches are modulated by AdaLN and combined through residual connections, enabling joint reasoning over noise, appearance, motion priors, and frame reliability. Unlike the morphological refinement applied to pseudo-labels before training, the diffusion module operates during inference to suppress residual noise and recover fine structures.

Temporal Consistency in Semi-supervised Learning. To promote temporal coherence, we incorporate a consistency loss that aligns predictions across adjacent frames. Let \mathcal{M}_t and \mathcal{M}_{t+1} be the predicted masks, and $\mathbf{F}_{t \rightarrow t+1}$ the optical flow:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{temp}} = \sum_{t=1}^{T-1} \left\| \mathcal{M}_t - \mathcal{W}(\mathcal{M}_{t+1}, \mathbf{F}_{t \rightarrow t+1}) \right\|^2, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathcal{W}(\cdot, \cdot)$ denotes a differentiable warping operator. The overall objective is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{seg}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{temp}}. \quad (10)$$

YOLO-based Mask Refinement. During inference, we apply a YOLO-based post-processing module [41] to detect anatomical regions of interest (ROIs). Predicted masks are cropped according to the detected bounding boxes, reducing false positives and improving spatial accuracy without affecting training.

4. Experiments

4.1. Dataset and Implementation

Dataset Analysis. We analyze the thyroid ultrasound dataset for temporal and spatial diversity (Fig. 3). Most sequences contain 50–100 frames, with a few longer cases (Fig. 3(a)). Masks typically occupy under 5% of a frame (Fig. 3(b)), consistent with small nodules, though larger lesions appear occasionally. Aspect ratios are usually 1.0–1.5, with some up to 2.4 (Fig. 3(c)). Such variations, together with low contrast and motion blur, motivate our adaptive pseudo-labeling and latent refinement.

The dataset includes 80 anonymized sequences totaling 5,334 frames, each annotated by experienced radiologists. The median length is 67 frames (IQR: 52–84). To preserve temporal continuity, we adopt a sequence-aware split, assigning all frames from the same video to a single partition, with training, validation, and test sets in a 7:1:2 ratio, adjusted to respect video boundaries.

For preprocessing, we apply contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) [37] to enhance local contrast. Frames are padded for RAFT compatibility and unpadded post-inference. Explicit intensity normalization is omitted, as the VAE inherently normalizes latent features for diffusion input.

4.2. Implementation Details

All experiments use PyTorch on an NVIDIA GPU (24GB VRAM). We train for 50 epochs with AdamW [28] (lr= 1×10^{-4} , cosine annealing, batch size 8) and gradient clipping (max norm 1.0). The diffusion module follows Polyp-DDPM [15], encoding each frame via a VAE before latent-space denoising, with a linear noise schedule from $\beta_{\text{start}} = 10^{-4}$ to $\beta_{\text{end}} = 0.02$ over 1000 steps.

Pseudo-labels are produced by a **frozen** RAFT model via bidirectional keyframe propagation, with flow fusion weight λ adaptively determined from keyframe histograms. Task Tokens are injected in each DiT block through cross-attention to incorporate temporal context. A sequence-aware split avoids data leakage. At inference, the diffusion model outputs refined masks, and YOLO-based post-processing suppresses background noise and sharpens boundaries.

4.3. Model Performance Comparison

We benchmark our method against a comprehensive set of state-of-the-art segmentation models, covering both convolutional and Transformer-based architectures. The evaluated baselines include UNet [38], UNet++ [62], TransUNet [5], SETR [61], and DAF [45], as well as video-level models such as ViViT [3], STM [33], MemSAM [12], and Vivim [56]. To evaluate generalization, we conduct experiments on both our curated thyroid dataset and the pub-

Figure 3. Statistical analysis of the Thyroid Ultrasound Dataset. (a) Frame count distribution across videos; (b) Distribution of mask area ratio (mask pixel count divided by image size); (c) Distribution of mask aspect ratio (width/height of mask bounding box). Red curves indicate Gaussian fits; gray dashed lines denote medians.

Table 1. Quantitative comparison with state-of-the-art methods under the semi-supervised setting using RAFT-based pseudo-labels. Dice, Jaccard, Precision, and Recall are reported on our dataset and the VTUS dataset [56]. Best scores are highlighted in bold.

Method	Venue	Type	Ours				VTUS			
			Jaccard	Dice	Precision	Recall	Jaccard	Dice	Precision	Recall
UNet [38]	MICCAI15	image	0.5256	0.6890	0.5919	0.8296	0.6585	0.7733	0.8145	0.8009
UNet++ [62]	DLMIA18	image	0.5561	0.7147	0.6217	0.8653	0.6838	0.7962	0.8317	0.8792
TransUNet [5]	arXiv21	image	0.6123	0.7595	0.7123	0.8894	0.6846	0.8093	0.8561	0.8961
SETR [61]	CVPR21	image	0.6234	0.7683	0.7212	0.8915	0.6835	0.7988	0.8352	0.8764
DAF [45]	MICCAI18	image	0.6048	0.7236	0.6599	0.8223	0.6766	0.7458	0.7974	0.8130
ViViT [3]	ICCV21	video	0.6328	0.7728	0.7321	0.8278	0.6715	0.7996	0.8324	0.8231
STM [33]	ICCV19	video	0.6296	0.7713	0.7187	0.8561	0.6701	0.8022	0.8253	0.8475
MemSAM [12]	CVPR24	video	0.6393	0.7814	0.7516	0.8567	0.6972	0.8153	0.8593	0.8659
Vivim [56]	TCSVT'25	video	0.6347	0.7741	0.7284	0.8721	0.7140	0.8114	0.7965	0.8838
VAR-DiT (Ours)	–	video	0.6472	0.7950	0.7688	0.8304	0.7162	0.8364	0.8827	0.8291

lic VTUS benchmark [56], which presents diverse clinical scenarios. All models are trained under a unified semi-supervised setup using RAFT-based pseudo-labels and consistent data splits.

Table 1 reports the results. Our model, VAR-DiT, consistently outperforms all baselines. It achieves the best Jaccard (0.6472) and Dice (0.7950) on the internal dataset, and establishes new VTUS records in Jaccard (0.7162), Dice (0.8364), and Precision (0.8827), demonstrating strong cross-domain robustness.

Compared to recent video-level methods such as MemSAM [12], ViViT [3], and Vivim [56], VAR-DiT delivers more stable and accurate segmentations, attributed to its latent denoising and autoregressive priors. Although SETR [61] and TransUNet [5] exhibit high recall, their lower precision indicates oversegmentation. VAR-DiT maintains better recall-precision balance, leading to more localized outputs.

Figure 4 shows representative predictions, including the ultrasound image, ground truth, and outputs from VAR-DiT

and five strong baselines. Our model produces smoother, more coherent masks with sharper boundaries, especially under low contrast or morphological ambiguity, matching the observed Dice gains. This alignment between qualitative and quantitative results supports its robustness in clinically challenging conditions.

4.4. Ablation Study

Model Component. To evaluate key components, we conduct an ablation on the YOLO-based post-processing module and the VAR encoder (Table 3). YOLO post-processing alone improves Jaccard and Dice by 1.0% and 1.1% by suppressing background noise and refining lesion boundaries. Adding the VAR encoder yields a further 1.3% and 1.2% improvement by capturing long-range temporal dependencies. These results confirm that spatial refinement and temporal context jointly enhance segmentation accuracy.

Pseudo-label Generation. As shown in Table 2, our RAFT-based method achieves the highest performance (Jaccard: 92.73%, Dice: 96.02%) with balanced precision and recall. This benefit comes from dense, frame-aware

Figure 4. Qualitative comparison of segmentation results across representative frames. Each row shows an ultrasound frame with its corresponding ground truth (GT) and predictions from six methods: our approach (VAR-DiT), DAF [45], MedSAM [30], TransUNet [5], SETR [61], and ViViT [3]. Our method demonstrates superior boundary adherence and robustness to shape variations and background noise, particularly in low-contrast or ambiguous regions, matching the observed improvements in Dice and Jaccard scores.

Table 2. Comparison of different pseudo-label generation methods. The best-performing method is highlighted in bold.

Pseudo-label Method	Jaccard (%)	Dice (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
MedicalSAM (Pre-trained)	78.74	85.14	80.32	90.28
Fine-tuned MedicalSAM	80.61	86.49	81.77	91.42
Classical CV (Two-side Flow Warp)	91.69	95.65	94.88	96.42
Distance-based Flow Fusion	87.95	93.52	90.65	96.61
Cross Pseudo Supervision (CPS) [8]	89.83	94.31	91.03	97.94
RAFT-based Optical Flow (Ours)	92.73	96.02	95.16	96.88

Table 3. Ablation study of key modules. The full model uses both YOLO post-processing and VAR encoder.

Configuration	Jaccard	Dice	Precision	Recall
Baseline	0.6238	0.7724	0.7450	0.8020
YOLO only	0.6341	0.7831	0.7551	0.8150
YOLO+VAR	0.6472	0.7950	0.7688	0.8304

flow and histogram-guided fusion, which preserve structural alignment even under low SNR and irregular motion. In contrast, prompt-driven MedicalSAM variants yield coarse masks, CPS [8] improves recall but blurs boundaries, and classical warping remains sensitive to motion artifacts.

Overall, robust pseudo-labeling with dual-branch conditioning delivers outputs that are both quantitatively superior and temporally coherent, which is essential for real-world clinical ultrasound analysis.

5. Conclusion

We propose a semi-supervised segmentation framework integrating bidirectional pseudo-label propagation, latent-space diffusion, and a Visual Autoregressive (VAR) encoder. The VAR extracts temporal context and injects autoregressive priors into Transformer blocks via cross-attention, improving boundary precision and temporal consistency.

By combining spatial denoising, temporal modeling, and adaptive supervision, our method tackles noise, scarce annotations, and motion-induced inconsistencies. Extensive experiments show consistent superiority over baselines across datasets and metrics, validating the effectiveness of the joint design.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by the Guangdong Science and Technology Department (No. 2024ZDZX2004).

References

- [1] Sharib Ali, Yamid Espinel, Yueming Jin, Peng Liu, Bianca Güttner, Xukun Zhang, Lihua Zhang, Tom Dowrick, Matthew J Clarkson, Shiting Xiao, et al. An objective comparison of methods for augmented reality in laparoscopic liver resection by preoperative-to-intraoperative image fusion. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.15753*, 2024. 1
- [2] Sharib Ali, Yamid Espinel, Yueming Jin, Peng Liu, Bianca Güttner, Xukun Zhang, Lihua Zhang, Tom Dowrick, Matthew J Clarkson, Shiting Xiao, et al. An objective comparison of methods for augmented reality in laparoscopic liver resection by preoperative-to-intraoperative image fusion from the miccai2022 challenge. *Medical image analysis*, 99:103371, 2025. 1
- [3] Anurag Arnab, Mostafa Dehghani, Georg Heigold, Chen Sun, Mario Lučić, and Cordelia Schmid. Vivit: A video vision transformer. In *IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 6836–6846, 2021. 1, 6, 7, 8
- [4] Huanran Chen, Yinpeng Dong, Zhengyi Wang, Xiao Yang, Chengqi Duan, Hang Su, and Jun Zhu. Robust classification via a single diffusion model. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.15241*, 2023. 3
- [5] Jieneng Chen, Yongyi Lu, Qihang Yu, Xiangde Luo, Ehsan Adeli, Yan Wang, Le Lu, Alan L Yuille, and Yuyin Zhou. Transunet: Transformers make strong encoders for medical image segmentation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2102.04306*, 2021. 2, 6, 7, 8
- [6] Shoufa Chen, Peize Sun, Yibing Song, and Ping Luo. Diffusiondet: Diffusion model for object detection. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2211.09788*, 2022. 3
- [7] Xi Chen, Diederik P Kingma, Tim Salimans, Yan Duan, Prafulla Dhariwal, John Schulman, Ilya Sutskever, and Pieter Abbeel. Variational lossy autoencoder. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1611.02731*, 2016. 5
- [8] Xiaokang Chen, Yuhui Yuan, Gang Zeng, and Jingdong Wang. Semi-supervised semantic segmentation with cross pseudo supervision. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 2613–2622, 2021. 8
- [9] Yifei Chen, Chenyan Zhang, Yifan Ke, Yiyu Huang, Xuezhou Dai, Feiwei Qin, Yongquan Zhang, Xiaodong Zhang, and Changmiao Wang. Semi-supervised medical image segmentation method based on cross-pseudo labeling leveraging strong and weak data augmentation strategies. In *2024 IEEE International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI)*, pages 1–5. IEEE, 2024. 1
- [10] Ho Kei Cheng, Yu-Wing Tai, and Chi-Keung Tang. Rethinking space-time networks with improved memory coverage for efficient video object segmentation. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 34:11781–11794, 2021. 3
- [11] Jianning Chi, Zelan Li, Zhiyi Sun, Xiaosheng Yu, and Huan Wang. Hybrid transformer unet for thyroid segmentation from ultrasound scans. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 153:106453, 2023. 3
- [12] Xiaolong Deng, Huisi Wu, Runhao Zeng, and Jing Qin. Memsam: Taming segment anything model for echocardiography video segmentation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 9622–9631, 2024. 3, 6, 7
- [13] Prafulla Dhariwal and Alexander Nichol. Diffusion models beat gans on image synthesis. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 34:8780–8794, 2021. 3
- [14] Min Dong, Ating Yang, Zhenhang Wang, Dezhen Li, Jing Yang, and Rongchang Zhao. Uncertainty-aware consistency learning for semi-supervised medical image segmentation. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 309:112890, 2025. 3
- [15] Zolnamar Dorjsembe, Hsing-Kuo Pao, and Furen Xiao. Polyp-ddpm: Diffusion-based semantic polyp synthesis for enhanced segmentation. In *2024 46th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)*, pages 1–7. IEEE, 2024. 6
- [16] Junkai Fan, Jiangwei Weng, Kun Wang, Yijun Yang, Jianjun Qian, Jun Li, and Jian Yang. Driving-video dehazing with non-aligned regularization for safety assistance. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 26109–26119, 2024. 3
- [17] Yunqi Gu, Tao Zhou, Yizhe Zhang, Yi Zhou, Kelei He, Chen Gong, and Huazhu Fu. Dual-scale enhanced and cross-generative consistency learning for semi-supervised medical image segmentation. *Pattern Recognition*, 158:110962, 2025. 3
- [18] Xizewen Han, Huangjie Zheng, and Mingyuan Zhou. Card: Classification and regression diffusion models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.07275*, 2022. 3
- [19] Ali Hatamizadeh, Yucheng Tang, Vishwesh Nath, Dong Yang, Andriy Myronenko, Bennett Landman, Holger R Roth, and Daguang Xu. Unetr: Transformers for 3d medical image segmentation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*, pages 574–584, 2022. 2
- [20] Yufan He, Vishwesh Nath, Dong Yang, Yucheng Tang, Andriy Myronenko, and Daguang Xu. Swinunetr-v2: Stronger swin transformers with stagewise convolutions for 3d medical image segmentation. In *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*, pages 416–426. Springer, 2023. 2
- [21] Jonathan Ho, Ajay Jain, and Pieter Abbeel. Denoising diffusion probabilistic models. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 33:6840–6851, 2020. 3
- [22] Reda Abdellah Kamraoui, Vinh-Thong Ta, Nicolas Papadakis, Fanny Compaire, José V Manjon, and Pierrick Coupé. Popcorn: Progressive pseudo-labeling with consistency regularization and neighboring. In *Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention—MICCAI 2021: 24th International Conference, Strasbourg, France, September 27–October 1, 2021, Proceedings, Part II 24*, pages 373–382. Springer, 2021. 3
- [23] Jialu Li, Qingqing Zheng, Mingshuang Li, Ping Liu, Qiong Wang, Litao Sun, and Lei Zhu. Rethinking breast lesion segmentation in ultrasound: A new video dataset and a baseline network. In *MICCAI*, pages 391–400. Springer, 2022. 3
- [24] Yuexiang Li, Jiawei Chen, Xinpeng Xie, Kai Ma, and Yefeng Zheng. Self-loop uncertainty: A novel pseudo-label for semi-supervised medical image segmentation. In *Medi-*

- cal Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention–MICCAI 2020: 23rd International Conference, Lima, Peru, October 4–8, 2020, Proceedings, Part I 23*, pages 614–623. Springer, 2020. 3
- [25] Yongqing Liang, Xin Li, Navid Jafari, and Jim Chen. Video object segmentation with adaptive feature bank and uncertain-region refinement. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 33:3430–3441, 2020. 3
- [26] Xiangbin Liu, Liping Song, Shuai Liu, and Yudong Zhang. A review of deep-learning-based medical image segmentation methods. *Sustainability*, 13(3):1224, 2021. 1
- [27] Xihui Liu, Dong Huk Park, Samaneh Azadi, Gong Zhang, Arman Chopikyan, Yuxiao Hu, Humphrey Shi, Anna Rohrbach, and Trevor Darrell. More control for free! image synthesis with semantic diffusion guidance. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*, 2023. 3
- [28] Ilya Loshchilov and Frank Hutter. Decoupled weight decay regularization. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.05101*, 2017. 6
- [29] Yingling Lu, Yijun Yang, Zhaohu Xing, Qiong Wang, and Lei Zhu. Diff-vps: Video polyp segmentation via a multi-task diffusion network with adversarial temporal reasoning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.07238*, 2024. 3
- [30] Jun Ma, Yuting He, Feifei Li, Lin Han, Chenyu You, and Bo Wang. Segment anything in medical images. *Nature Communications*, 15(1):654, 2024. 1, 8
- [31] Laifa Ma, Guanghua Tan, Hongxia Luo, Qing Liao, Shengli Li, and Kenli Li. A novel deep learning framework for automatic recognition of thyroid gland and tissues of neck in ultrasound image. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology*, 32(9):6113–6124, 2022. 3
- [32] Seoung Wug Oh, Joon-Young Lee, Kalyan Sunkavalli, and Seon Joo Kim. Fast video object segmentation by reference-guided mask propagation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 7376–7385, 2018. 1
- [33] Seoung Wug Oh, Joon-Young Lee, Ning Xu, and Seon Joo Kim. Video object segmentation using space-time memory networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 9226–9235, 2019. 3, 6, 7
- [34] Qingtao Pan, Zhengrong Li, Wenhao Qiao, Jingjiao Lou, Qing Yang, Guang Yang, and Bing Ji. Amvln: Alignment-multiplicity aware vision-language model for semi-supervised medical image segmentation. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, 2025. 3
- [35] William Peebles and Saining Xie. Scalable diffusion models with transformers. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*, pages 4195–4205, 2023. 6
- [36] Pinle Qin, Kuan Wu, Yishan Hu, Jianchao Zeng, and Xiangfei Chai. Diagnosis of benign and malignant thyroid nodules using combined conventional ultrasound and ultrasound elasticity imaging. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 24(4):1028–1036, 2019. 2
- [37] Ali M Reza. Realization of the contrast limited adaptive histogram equalization (clahe) for real-time image enhancement. *Journal of VLSI signal processing systems for signal, image and video technology*, 38:35–44, 2004. 6
- [38] Olaf Ronneberger, Philipp Fischer, and Thomas Brox. U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation. In *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-assisted Intervention (MICCAI)*, pages 234–241. Springer, 2015. 6, 7
- [39] Jaskirat Singh, Stephen Gould, and Liang Zheng. High-fidelity guided image synthesis with latent diffusion models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2211.17084*, 2022. 3
- [40] Pranav Singh, Raviteja Chukkappalli, Shravan Chaudhari, Luoyao Chen, Mei Chen, Jinqian Pan, Craig Smuda, and Jacopo Cirrone. Shifting to machine supervision: annotation-efficient semi and self-supervised learning for automatic medical image segmentation and classification. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1):10820, 2024. 1
- [41] Joseph Sobek, Jose R Medina Inojosa, Betsy J Medina Inojosa, SM Rassoulinejad-Mousavi, Gian Marco Conte, Francisco Lopez-Jimenez, and Bradley J Erickson. Medyolo: a medical image object detection framework. *Journal of Imaging Informatics in Medicine*, pages 1–9, 2024. 6
- [42] Jiaming Song, Chenlin Meng, and Stefano Ermon. Denoising diffusion implicit models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.02502*, 2020. 3
- [43] Zachary Teed and Jia Deng. Raft: Recurrent all-pairs field transforms for optical flow. In *Computer Vision–ECCV 2020: 16th European Conference, Glasgow, UK, August 23–28, 2020, Proceedings, Part II 16*, pages 402–419. Springer, 2020. 1, 4
- [44] Tao Wang, Zhongzheng Huang, Jiawei Wu, Yuanzheng Cai, and Zuoyong Li. Semi-supervised medical image segmentation with co-distribution alignment. *Bioengineering*, 10(7):869, 2023. 1
- [45] Yi Wang, Zijun Deng, Xiaowei Hu, Lei Zhu, Xin Yang, Xuemiao Xu, Pheng-Ann Heng, and Dong Ni. Deep attentional features for prostate segmentation in ultrasound. In *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-assisted Intervention (MICCAI)*, pages 523–530. Springer, 2018. 2, 6, 7, 8
- [46] Julia Wolleb, Robin Sandkühler, Florentin Bieder, Philippe Valmaggia, and Philippe C Cattin. Diffusion models for implicit image segmentation ensembles. In *International Conference on Medical Imaging with Deep Learning*, pages 1336–1348. PMLR, 2022. 3
- [47] Hongtao Wu, Yijun Yang, Haoyu Chen, Jingjing Ren, and Lei Zhu. Mask-guided progressive network for joint raindrop and rain streak removal in videos. In *Proceedings of the 31st ACM International Conference on Multimedia*, pages 7216–7225, 2023. 3
- [48] Hongtao Wu, Yijun Yang, Angelica I Aviles-Rivero, Jingjing Ren, Sixiang Chen, Haoyu Chen, and Lei Zhu. Semi-supervised video desnowing network via temporal decoupling experts and distribution-driven contrastive regularization. In *European Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 70–89. Springer, 2024. 1, 3
- [49] Hanguang Xiao, Yangjian Wang, Shidong Xiong, Yanjun Ren, and Hongmin Zhang. Cuamt: A mri semi-supervised

- medical image segmentation framework based on contextual information and mixed uncertainty. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, page 108755, 2025. 3
- [50] Zhaohu Xing, Liang Wan, Huazhu Fu, Guang Yang, Yijun Yang, Lequan Yu, Baiying Lei, and Lei Zhu. Diff-unet: A diffusion embedded network for robust 3d medical image segmentation. *Medical Image Analysis*, page 103654, 2025. 3
- [51] Yijun Yang, Shujun Wang, Lei Zhu, and Lequan Yu. Hcdg: A hierarchical consistency framework for domain generalization on medical image segmentation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2109.05742*, 2021. 2
- [52] Yijun Yang, Angelica I Aviles-Rivero, Huazhu Fu, Ye Liu, Weiming Wang, and Lei Zhu. Video adverse-weather-component suppression network via weather messenger and adversarial backpropagation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 13200–13210, 2023. 1
- [53] Yijun Yang, Huazhu Fu, Angelica I Aviles-Rivero, Carola-Bibiane Schönlieb, and Lei Zhu. Diffmic: Dual-guidance diffusion network for medical image classification. In *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*, pages 95–105. Springer, 2023. 3
- [54] Yijun Yang, Shujun Wang, Lihao Liu, Sarah Hickman, Fiona J Gilbert, Carola-Bibiane Schönlieb, and Angelica I Aviles-Rivero. Mammodg: Generalisable deep learning breaks the limits of cross-domain multi-center breast cancer screening. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.01057*, 2023. 2
- [55] Yijun Yang, Hongtao Wu, Angelica I Aviles-Rivero, Yulun Zhang, Jing Qin, and Lei Zhu. Genuine knowledge from practice: Diffusion test-time adaptation for video adverse weather removal. In *2024 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 25606–25616. IEEE, 2024. 3
- [56] Yijun Yang, Zhaohu Xing, and Lei Zhu. Vivim: a video vision mamba for medical video object segmentation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.14168*, 2024. 1, 6, 7
- [57] Yijun Yang, Huazhu Fu, Angelica I Aviles-Rivero, Zhaohu Xing, and Lei Zhu. Diffmic-v2: Medical image classification via improved diffusion network. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, 2025. 3
- [58] Yijun Yang, Zhao-Yang Wang, Qiuping Liu, Shuwen Sun, Kang Wang, Rama Chellappa, Zongwei Zhou, Alan Yuille, Lei Zhu, Yu-Dong Zhang, et al. Medical world model: Generative simulation of tumor evolution for treatment planning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2506.02327*, 2025. 1
- [59] Zhao Yang, Qiang Wang, Luca Bertinetto, Weiming Hu, Song Bai, and Philip HS Torr. Anchor diffusion for unsupervised video object segmentation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*, pages 931–940, 2019. 1
- [60] Lvmin Zhang, Anyi Rao, and Maneesh Agrawala. Adding conditional control to text-to-image diffusion models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 3836–3847, 2023. 3
- [61] Sixiao Zheng, Jiachen Lu, Hengshuang Zhao, Xiatian Zhu, Zekun Luo, Yabiao Wang, Yanwei Fu, Jianfeng Feng, Tao Xiang, Philip HS Torr, et al. Rethinking semantic segmentation from a sequence-to-sequence perspective with transformers. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 6881–6890, 2021. 6, 7, 8
- [62] Zongwei Zhou, Md Mahfuzur Rahman Siddiquee, Nima Tajbakhsh, and Jianming Liang. Unet++: A nested u-net architecture for medical image segmentation. In *Deep learning in medical image analysis and multimodal learning for clinical decision support: 4th international workshop, DLMIA 2018, and 8th international workshop, ML-CDS 2018, held in conjunction with MICCAI 2018, Granada, Spain, September 20, 2018, proceedings 4*, pages 3–11. Springer, 2018. 6, 7